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**APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN BUSINESS EDUCATION RESEARCH IN
UNIVERSITIES IN SOUTH-SOUTH NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the application of artificial intelligence in business education research within universities in the South-South region of Nigeria. The study was guided by two research questions and four hypotheses. A descriptive survey research design was employed. The study population consisted of 232 business education lecturers, made up of 138 lecturers from state universities and 94 from federal universities. Given the manageable size, the entire population was used as the sample. Data were collected using a 37-item questionnaire developed by the researchers. The instrument was designed on a four-point rating scale: Very High Extent (4), High Extent (3), Low Extent (2), and Very Low Extent (1). Both face and content validity of the questionnaire were established through expert review by two computer science specialists, three experts in measurement and evaluation, and two business education experts from Delta State University, Abraka. To determine the reliability of the instrument, 18 copies of the questionnaire were pilot-tested on 18 business education lecturers at Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, located in South-East Nigeria and outside the study area. The responses were analyzed using Cronbach's Alpha, yielding reliability coefficients of 0.86 and 0.89 for the two research questions, indicating high internal consistency. A total of 243 questionnaires were distributed to business education lecturers, of which 232 were correctly completed and returned within two weeks, representing a response rate of 95.47%. The collected data were analyzed using mean scores and standard deviations, while independent samples t-test was employed to test the hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. Decisions on the hypotheses were based on comparing the calculated t-values with the critical t-values. Findings related to the first research question indicated that strategies for enhancing the use of artificial intelligence in business education research include improved funding for AI-related research infrastructure and the availability of data to support AI-driven research activities. Results from the second research question revealed several challenges, such as the absence of comprehensive public policies on AI application in education and research, as well as limited understanding of adaptive learning algorithms necessary for effective AI-based research. The hypotheses testing showed, among other outcomes, that there was no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female lecturers regarding strategies for promoting the application of artificial intelligence in business education research in South-South Nigerian universities. Based on these findings, the study recommended that university authorities should provide adequate funding for workshops and conferences aimed at equipping lecturers with relevant skills and strategies for applying artificial intelligence in business education research.

Keywords: Application, Artificial Intelligence, Business Education, Research

INTRODUCTION

Business educators bear a significant responsibility to prepare students for success in a constantly changing and fast-paced world of work. It is crucial for Business educators to persistently adjust to the most recent trends and changes in the

world of work, ensuring that their curricula stay relevant and aligned with the ever-changing fluctuations. Business educators should ensure that their graduates are equipped with the essential knowledge and competencies by emphasizing practical, hands-on learning. Business education programme and entrepreneurship practices play a crucial role in shaping the future for self-reliance and propelling the accomplishments of their graduates. (Amahi, Otomiewo & Egeonu, 2025). The importance of Business Education research to skill acquisition, employability of the teaming youths and national development at large cannot be overemphasized. For instance, Ekwue et al. (2022) describe Business Education as an academic programme designed to provide learners with relevant skills, knowledge, attitudes, and values required for effective participation in the workplace, self-sufficiency, and overall national development. Ore, et al. (2022) justify that Business Education equips learners with the required knowledge, vocational skills and aptitude to effectively manage personal businesses and at the same time function effectively in the economic system.

According to Celik et al. (2022), the concept of artificial intelligence was formally introduced in 1956 by John McCarthy. Baker and Smith (2019) in Celik et al. (2022), point out that Artificial intelligence does not refer to a single technology but is defined as “computers (that) perform cognitive tasks, usually associated with human minds, particularly learning and problem-solving”. AI is a general term that refers to diverse systematic methods. These methods can be classified as machine learning, neural networks, and deep learning. Artificial intelligence refers to the capacity of computer systems or computer-controlled machines to carry out tasks that typically require human intelligence, such as reasoning and decision-making for effective job performance. Similarly, Nwanguma and Onyeukwu (2023) define artificial intelligence as the ability of digital computers or automated systems to execute functions traditionally associated with human intellectual capabilities. UNESCO (2019) report that Artificial Intelligence has the potential to address some of the biggest challenges in education to stimulate innovate teaching and learning practices, research and accelerated progress towards attaining rapid national development. The use of Artificial Intelligence in education and research according to Chen, Xie and Hwang (2020) include the use of intelligent tutoring systems, teaching robots, learning analytics, dash boards, adaptive learning systems, human-computer interactions, data collection, data cleaning, analysis and reporting among others. Ouyang and Jiao (2021) affirm that the implications of Artificial Intelligence hold significant potential for the research process as in most qualitative researches and organized data by applying short, descriptive codes to segments of text, making it easier to summarize large sets of data. Fabricio (2023) observes that unleashing the significance of Artificial Intelligence in academia and research is like opening a treasure chest of limitless possibilities to researchers to dive into the future research activities where Artificial Intelligence is a prerequisite for effective business education research in Nigerian Universities (Ofume, 2025).

Research is at the centre of human development as no human society can witness meaningful development without innovation and intensive research effort. Research is an academic process of identifying a problem, developing set of objectives that must be achieved, systematically making an inquiry into the identified problem through collection of data, careful analysis of data, interpretation of results, making deductions and drawing conclusion to add to the body of knowledge in accordance with methodologies of the professional field or discipline (Amusa and Hamzat, 2024). According to Muresan and Gogu (2012), tertiary institutions such as universities represent major promoters of research and innovation for the development of new solutions in the technological and socioeconomic areas of human societies. The Institute of Academic Development (2020) equally notes that research targets mostly the provision of solutions to wide research questions. It is important to note that Artificial Intelligence is a major tool in educational research particularly, in business education programme which all Universities should adapt to.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Business education is education for and about business which enables the university graduates to be self-employed after the completion of their programme. In business education programme, there are four major components namely: accounting, marketing, management, and office technology and management that helps to impact skills and competencies to graduates. Despite the relevance of Artificial Intelligence in the educational system, it is unfortunate to know that the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) for research in business education has not been taken into effective use. The statement of the problem therefore is what is the extent of application of artificial intelligence in business education research?

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of the study is to assess the extent of application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in business education research. Specifically, the objectives are:

1. To determine the extent of strategies for stimulating the application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research in South-South Universities in Nigeria.
2. To determine the extent of challenges in the application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent are the strategies for stimulating the application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research in South-South Universities in Nigeria?
2. To what extent are the challenges in the application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research in South-South Universities in Nigeria?

HYPOTHESES

The following hypotheses are tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean rating between male and female lecturers on the strategies for stimulating the application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research in South-South Universities in Nigeria.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean rating between male and female lecturers on the challenges of application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research in South-South Universities in Nigeria.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean rating between state and federal university lecturers on the strategies for stimulating the application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research in South-South Universities in Nigeria.
4. There is no significant difference in the mean rating between state and federal university lecturers on the challenges of application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Empirical Studies

Ofume (2025) investigated the challenges and strategic approaches associated with the application of artificial intelligence (AI) in business education research within Nigerian tertiary institutions. The study focused on the South-South region of Nigeria, specifically selecting Bayelsa and Delta States from the six states in the region. Using a multistage random sampling technique, the study sampled 175 respondents, comprising 143 business education lecturers and 32 business education instructors. Data were collected through a structured 30-item questionnaire. Mean and standard deviation were employed to answer the research questions, while t-test statistics were used to test the hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. The analysis revealed fifteen major challenges confronting the use of AI in business education research, as well as twelve strategic measures for enhancing its application. The hypothesis testing indicated a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in the mean ratings of lecturers and instructors regarding the challenges of AI application. However, no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) was found between their mean ratings on the proposed strategic measures. Based on these findings, the study recommended, among other measures, the development and implementation of appropriate AI-related policies to promote effective integration of artificial intelligence in education and research activities in Nigeria.

Similarly, Amahi, Otomiewo, and Egeonu (2025) conducted a study titled Application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education Programme and Entrepreneurship Practice: Issues and Challenges. The study was guided by two research questions and two null hypotheses and adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population comprised all lecturers in the Department of Vocational and Technical Education, Faculty of Education, University of Delta, Agbor, during the 2023/2024 academic session. Due to the relatively small population size of thirty (30) lecturers, the entire population was used, eliminating the need for sampling. A structured questionnaire served as the instrument for data collection. Findings from the study indicated that the application of artificial intelligence in business education and entrepreneurship practices at the University of Delta, Agbor, was constrained by several factors, including issues of inclusion and equity, high maintenance costs, and inadequate preparation of teachers for AI-driven instruction. Based on the results, the authors concluded and recommended, among other things, that AI adoption strategies should be inclusive and accommodate all business educators, regardless of disparities arising from the digital divide.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a descriptive survey research design, which was considered appropriate because it allows for the collection of data without manipulating any variables (Okoro, 2024). The investigation was guided by two research questions and four hypotheses. The target population consisted of 232 business education lecturers drawn from universities in the study area, including 138 lecturers from state universities and 94 from federal universities. Owing to the manageable size of the population, the entire population was used as the sample, and no sampling technique was applied.

Data for the study were collected using a structured questionnaire comprising 37 items. The instrument was organised into two sections. Section A contained five items designed to elicit demographic information from the respondents, including name of university, type of university, academic rank, sex, and years of job experience. Section B consisted of 32 items derived from the two research questions. Specifically, 13 items addressed Research Question One, which focused on the extent to which strategies are employed to stimulate the application of artificial intelligence in business education research in

South-South Nigerian universities, while 19 items addressed Research Question Two, which examined the extent of challenges affecting the application of artificial intelligence in business education research in the same context.

The questionnaire was rated on a four-point Likert-type scale of Very High Extent (4), High Extent (3), Low Extent (2), and Very Low Extent (1). Both face and content validity of the instrument were established through expert judgment. The questionnaire was reviewed by two specialists in computer science, three experts in measurement and evaluation, and two business education experts from Delta State University, Abraka. Their comments and recommendations were incorporated before producing the final version of the instrument.

To determine the reliability of the questionnaire, a pilot test was conducted using 18 copies administered to 18 business education lecturers at Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, in South-East Nigeria, which was outside the study area. The responses obtained were analysed using Cronbach’s Alpha, resulting in a reliability coefficient of 0.86, indicating a high level of internal consistency.

A total of 243 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to respondents, and 232 were duly completed and returned within two weeks, representing a response rate of 95.47%. The collected data were weighted and analysed using mean scores, with values assigned as follows: Very High Extent (4), High Extent (3), Low Extent (2), and Very Low Extent (1). A mean score of 2.50 and above was interpreted as indicating a high extent, while a mean score below 2.50 signified a low extent. The hypotheses were tested using t-test statistics at the 0.05 level of significance. Decisions were made by comparing the calculated t-values with the critical t-values, where hypotheses were accepted when the calculated value was less than the critical value and rejected when it exceeded the critical value.

RESULT

Research Question 1: To what extent are the strategies for stimulating the application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research in South-South Universities in Nigeria? N = 232

Table 1: Mean responses of male and female on strategies for stimulating the Application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research in South-South Universities in Nigeria. N = 232.

S/N	What are the strategies for stimulating the application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research	\bar{x}	Std. Dev	Decision
1	Improved funding of business education research with AI facilities	3.33	0.82	HE
2	Provision of data for assisting AI-powered business education research	3.06	0.62	HE
3	Provision of strong internet services to stimulate the use of AI in business education research	3.09	0.75	HE
4	Integration of AI in business education curriculum for increased teaching and learning of AI	3.18	0.85	HE
5	Priority on AI-related researches in business education	3.23	0.84	HE
6	Incorporation of local contents into AI configuration in business education research	3.24	0.83	HE
7	Adequate provision of necessary infrastructure and AI-driven facilities in business education research	3.22	0.85	HE
8	Provision of stable electricity in Nigerian schools for effective use of AI in research	3.21	0.87	HE
9	Formulation of AI-driven policies by government for enhancing adoption of AI in business education research	3.24	0.90	HE
10	Increased awareness creation on the need for adoption of AI-powered instruction in business education	3.20	0.81	HE
11	Continuous training and retraining of business educators on effective use of AI	3.14	0.81	HE

12	Special intervention fund for Artificial Intelligence – powered business education research	3.15	0.84	HE
13	Establishment of Artificial Intelligence (AI) units in business education department	3.19	0.81	HE
	Aggregate Mean	3.19	0.82	

Research Question 2: To what extent are the challenges in the application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research in South-South Universities in Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean responses of male and female on challenges in the Application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research in South-South Universities in Nigeria. N = 232.

S/N	Challenges in the application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research are:	\bar{x}	Std. Dev	Decision
1	Inadequate comprehensive public policy on application of AI in education and research	3.14	0.82	HE
2	Poor ideas of adaptive learning algorithms required for the use of AI for research conduct	3.16	0.85	HE
3	insufficient funding of research and resources required for application of AI in research	3.18	0.80	HE
4	inadequate infrastructure for effective use of AI for researches in Nigerian tertiary institutions	3.29	0.81	HE
5	Unwillingness of education administrators to embrace AI	3.23	0.84	HE
6	Inadequate power supply in the application of AI	3.14	0.78	HE
7	Exclusion of wide population in the application of AI-powered education	3.15	0.76	HE
8	Exclusion of wide population in the application of AI-powered research	3.24	0.88	HE
9	Fear of human job loss constitutes a major hindrance in application of AI	3.25	0.83	HE
10	Wide skill gap in effective application of AI in Nigerian education and researches	3.22	0.84	HE
11	Digital illiteracy as a hindrance in effective application of AI in Nigerian universities	3.26	0.87	HE
12	Unwillingness to adopt the use of AI by researchers	3.17	0.86	HE
13	High cost of training of researchers in effective use of AI in Nigerian universities	3.22	0.76	HE
14	High cost of reliable data for effective AI-powered research in Nigerian universities	3.26	0.81	HE
15	Weak educational framework for teaching and learning of AI in Nigerian universities	3.19	0.88	HE
16	Lack of adherence of foreign researchers to the use of AI for research	3.21	0.79	HE
17	Very weak internet services and connection constitute a challenge in the use of AI for research	3.14	0.82	HE
18	Low level of awareness of AI-powered research among lecturers	3.23	0.78	HE
19	Inadequate AI local contents in its adoption in Nigerian universities	3.16	0.87	HE
	Aggregate Mean	3.21	0.82	HE

Testing of the Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean rating between male and female on the strategies for stimulating the application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

Table 3: Mean ratings between male and female lecturers on strategies for stimulating the application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research in South-South Universities in Nigeria

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t-cal.	df	t. value	Decision
Male	134	3.23	0.86	1.08	230	1.96	Accepted
Female	88	3.14	0.84				

Since the t-cal (1.08) is less than t. value 1.96 at significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean rating between male and female on the challenges of application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

Table 4: Mean ratings between male and female on challenges of application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t-cal.	df	t. value	Decision
Male	134	3.18	0.82	1.18	230	1.96	Accepted
Female	88	3.06	0.94				

Since the t-cal (1.18) is less than t. value 1.96 at significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the mean rating between state and federal university lecturers on the strategies for stimulating the application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research in South-South Universities in Nigeria

Table 5: Mean ratings between state and federal university lecturers on the strategies for stimulating the application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research in South-South Universities in Nigeria

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t-cal.	df	t. value	Decision
State	138	3.26	0.81	1.04	230	1.96	Accepted
Federal	94	3.14	0.84				

Since the t-cal (1.04) is less than t. value 1.96 at significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted.

H₀₄: There is no significant difference in the mean rating between state and federal university lecturers on the challenges of application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

Table 6: Mean ratings between state and federal university lecturers on the challenges of application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research in South-South Universities in Nigeria

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t-cal.	df	t. value	Decision
State	138	3.06	0.83	1.16	230	1.96	Accepted
Federal	94	3.01	0.86				

Since the t-cal (1.16) is less than t. value 1.96 at significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings on research question one reveal that the strategies for stimulating the application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research in South-South Universities in Nigeria are to a high extent. Some of these strategies are improved funding of business education research with AI facilities, provision of data for assisting AI-powered business education research, provision of strong internet services to stimulate the use of AI in business education research, integration of AI in business education curriculum for increased teaching and learning of AI, priority on AI-related researches in business education, incorporation of local contents into AI configuration in business education research, adequate provision of necessary infrastructure and AI-driven facilities in business education research, provision of stable electricity in Nigerian schools for effective use of AI in research, formulation of AI-driven policies by government for enhancing adoption of AI in business education research, Increased awareness creation on the need for adoption of AI-powered instruction in business education, Continuous training and retraining of business educators on effective use of AI, special intervention fund for Artificial Intelligence – powered business education research and establishment of Artificial Intelligence (AI) units in business education department. The findings are consistent with earlier studies of Ofume (2025), Amahi, Otomiewo & Egeonu (2025) who earlier identified the strategies for stimulating the application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research.

The findings of the hypotheses on research question 1 are: There is no significant difference in the mean rating between male and female on the strategies for stimulating the application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research in South-South Universities in Nigeria and there is no significant difference in the mean rating between state and federal university lecturers on the strategies for stimulating the application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

The findings on research question two reveal that the challenges in the application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research in South-South Universities in Nigeria are to a high extent. Some of these challenges are Inadequate comprehensive public policy on application of AI in education and research, poor ideas of adaptive learning algorithms required for the use of AI for research conduct, insufficient funding of research and resources required for application of AI in research, inadequate infrastructure for effective use of AI for researches in Nigeria tertiary institutions, unwillingness of education administrators to embrace AI, inadequate power supply in the application of AI, exclusion of wide population in the application of AI-powered education, exclusion of wide population in the application of AI-powered research, fear of human job loss will constitute a major hindrance in application of AI, wide skill gap in effective application of AI in Nigerian education and researches, digital illiteracy as a hindrance in effective application of AI in Nigerian

universities, unwillingness to adopt the use of AI by researchers, high cost of training of researchers in effective use of AI in Nigeria universities, high cost of reliable data for effective AI-powered research in Nigerian universities, weak educational framework for teaching and learning of AI in Nigeria universities, lack of adherence of foreign researchers to the use of AI for research, very weak internet services and connection constitute a challenge in the use of AI for research, low level of awareness of AI-powered research among lecturers in research and inadequate AI local contents in its adoption in Nigerian universities. The findings are consistent with earlier studies of Ofume (2025), Amahi, Otomiewo & Egeonu (2025) who earlier identified challenges in the application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education.

The findings of the hypotheses on research question 2 are: There is no significant difference in the mean rating between male and female on the challenges of application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research in South-South Universities in Nigeria and there is no significant difference in the mean rating between state and federal university lecturers on the challenges of application of Artificial Intelligence in Business Education research in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

The application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in business education programme in Universities in South-South Nigeria is paramount for effective business education research for all students and lecturers. The integration of AI technologies provides benefits such as enhanced personalized learning, streamlined administrative tasks, improved research efforts, facilitates collaboration, and the need to address ethical considerations. Since artificial intelligence is dynamic, lecturers should consolidate on continued learning process in Information Communication Technology driven era to overcome some inherent challenges in the world of work.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are made for the study:

1. School authorities should provide adequate funding for workshop conferences for lecturers on strategies for the application of AI on business education research.
2. School authorities should provide adequate comprehensive public policy on application of AI in business education programmes.
3. School authorities should provide relevant activities for improving lecturers' adaptive learning methods required for the use of AI for business education research.

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